

Lived Experiences of The Parents of Cyberbullied Grade 10 Students During The Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the parents of cyberbullied grade 10 students of Peniel Integrated Christian Academy during the covid-19 pandemic to help guidance counselors and school administrators to provide proper parenting, communicating, and coping strategies in working with parents and families (family-school collaboration) in promoting cyberbullying interventions and programs. The researcher utilized a qualitative approach using a phenomenological research design to better understand a phenomenon by relying on the experiences or viewpoints of the parents. The respondents were eight parents or primary caregivers (4 mothers, 3 fathers, and 1 guardian) of an adolescent aged 15-16 years, Grade 10 pupils of Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal who was cyberbullied within the school year 2020-2021 during the pandemic and were interviewed through an in-depth interview in the First Quarter of the school year 2021-2022. The interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis. As a result, the researcher came up with three themes which were extracted from the data: (1) Parent's Frustrations, where even though the parents were not the victim, all the parents experienced unpleasant emotional responses (2) Inadequate Support, where a lack of available support constrained the participants' attempts at mediation. There was no clear process for dealing with the problem efficiently, and (3) Proper programs and communication to parents, where the parents are aware of their responsibility in providing standards for proper online behavior to their children and teenagers, which includes offering education and action in the case of cyberbullying. Based on the data gathered, cyberbullying impacts the entire family, specifically the parents, not just the affected individual or student. The participants' lack of awareness of cyberbullying emphasizes the need for more excellent cyberbullying education. While it has been discovered that parents do not consider cyberbullying as an essential issue until it directly affects them, reacting to adolescent cyberbullying is a reality that many parents encounter daily. This study's findings may be utilized to suggest an increased need for cyberbullying intervention programs that better educate parents to mediate cyberbullying events.

INTRODUCTION

Bullying, as defined by Peniel Integrated Christian Academy Handbook (2020), is when a student commits an act or a series of acts directed towards another student, or a series of single acts directed to many students in a school setting, which results in physical and mental abuse, intimidation, harassment or humiliation. Cyberbullying is defined by the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) as "bullying using digital technologies." It can occur "on social media, messaging platforms, gaming platforms, and mobile phones repeatedly and intentionally." It is a pattern of behavior intended to frighten, anger, or shame individuals who are being targeted" (Nortajuddin, 2021). The following characteristics define cyberbullying: A *voluntary act* is one in which the activity is intentional and not inadvertent; a *recurring act* is one in which the conduct is repeated over time rather than limited to a single occurrence; The *victim's perception of injury*, in which the sufferer suffers the caused damage; which can happen *online* in social media, forums, and games utilizing technological gadgets (Ferrara et al., 2018).

Furthermore, cyberbullying is common among teens and might include name-calling, impersonation, or intentionally prohibiting someone from participating in social activities online. Harassment via social media, text messages, emails, instant messaging, or group chats is also considered cyberbullying. (Ioannou et al., 2017; Ozdemir, 2014; Robinson, 2013). Cyberbullying victims have reported a variety of emotional and physical health repercussions, as well as academic and interpersonal issues. Studies have shown that parents' awareness of their children's engagement in cyberbullying, whether as perpetrators or victims, is low (Wachs et al., 2020; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2019; Ortega Barón et al., 2018). Parents believe that schools will deal with cyberbullying. In contrast, schools argue that it is the

responsibility of the families to be involved (Cassidy, Faucher & Jackson, 2018). Regardless of who bears responsibility, research participants in studies on cyberbullying among children and youth have consistently supported a range of responses, including cyberbullying education for all parties involved (students, parents, and school staff), clear and well-implemented cyberbullying policies, improved reporting mechanisms, and more support for victims (Ranney et al., 2020).

COVID-19-related national lockdowns and extensive school closures significantly increased the online activity of millions of students throughout the world. As a result of these circumstances, there is an increasing rate of cyberbullying victimization among adolescents (Armitage, 2021). Given these risks, parents are encouraged to collaborate with schools in promoting cyberbullying interventions and programs during this period of confinement (Yang, 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to know the lived experiences of the parents of cyberbullied adolescents during the pandemic. The study will explore how the parents provided emotional support to their cyberbullied child, how they seek help from people outside their family, and their coping mechanism about the issue.

Cyberbullying Defined

Although there is a growing body of research on cyberbullying, several schools of thought on how the term should be defined (Capurso et al., 2017; Corcoran, Guckin, & Prentice, 2015; Goldstein, 2015). The purposeful nature of harm delivered to another individual using electronic means is a common aspect across definitions of cyberbullying. Impersonation online, spreading rumors, sending threatening messages, sending inappropriate photos, or harassment via text messaging, instant messaging, or chat rooms are all examples of electronic damage (Capurso et al., 2017). The terms cyberbullying, online bullying, online harassment, online peer harassment, cyberaggression, cyber harassment, and cyber victimhood have been used interchangeably (Corcoran et al., 2015).

According to Hinduja & Patchin (2019), when someone persistently and purposely harasses, mistreats, or mocks another person online or while using cell phones or other electronic devices, this is known as cyberbullying. The following are some of the most popular cyberbullying tactics: Making nasty, damaging, or embarrassing comments or rumors about someone over the internet, threatening to harm someone or encouraging them to commit suicide, making a derogatory or unpleasant image or video public, pretending to be someone else in order to solicit or disseminate personal or misleading information about someone else on the internet and making a derogatory or cruel webpage about another person.

Characteristics of Cyberbullying

According to Barlett et al. (2016), while all bullying is defined by intentional, often recurrent, cruel action directed towards another person or group, some characteristics identify it when it occurs online or by smartphone, such as (1) Persistent. Because most adolescents have constant access to some technology, cyberbullying can occur anytime—morning, afternoon, or evening—rather than simply during school. It might happen at home or in the neighborhood. (2) Hard to Detect. While some forms of bullying are evident, such as pushing or damaging property, cyberbullying occurs on phones, computers, or tablets, making it far more difficult for adults to notice. (3) Anonymous. Cyberbullying can be carried out under the guise of anonymity. Those bullied may not even realize who is doing the bullying, making it possible for one adolescent to damage another without being held accountable. (4) Capable of spreading to a much larger audience. Information may be exchanged rapidly and fast over the internet, making it difficult to control or prevent nasty comments from spreading. (5) Easier to be hurtful. Because of the more considerable physical distance, it is generally simpler to bully via technology. Because technology separates the students from the real-life, they may not perceive the severe harm caused by their acts. (6) Permanent. When something is shared on the internet, it is frequently accessible by anybody, anywhere. It can be difficult to remove data once uploaded on the internet entirely.

Types of Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying is a very complex phenomenon comprised of various sorts of behavior discussed here.

Flaming uses an electronic device to send violent and vulgar messages to create verbal battles between two or more network users. The victim may or may not always be present (Qodir et al., 2019). Flaming can occur during a chat conversation or participating in interactive video games. The majority of flame occurs in interactive games because the victims are often inexperienced players targeted by more experienced players (Sung Je et al., 2019).

Harassment is defined as sending a specific person frequent and offensive communication that causes significant psychological and emotional pain. Harassment can occur via email, texts, forums, chat rooms, and discussion boards

(Wells et al., 2019). As in traditional bullying, the victim is constantly "one down" and passively suffers from aggression (Choi and Kruis, 2020; Moneva et al., 2020).

Cyberstalking is when someone is harassed, threatened, or persecuted online to isolate and intimidate them. The cyberstalker has virtual power over their victims and follows them around. The persecutor may repeatedly contact the victim, sending nasty and intrusive messages (Reyns and Fissel, 2020). Anonymity safeguards the cyberstalker, who frequently establishes bogus profiles. Thus, it raises the level of disinhibition (the effect) and animosity against the victim (Dhillon and Smith, 2019; Saladino et al., 2020).

Denigration entails sending false or harmful communications to victims to harm their reputation or friendships. Frequently, the persecutor sends or publishes photos, photographs, or videos of the victim (Sangwan and Bhatia, 2020).

Impersonation occurs when a cyberbully obtains access to the victim's personal account information (name and password) and uses it to impersonate the target online, posting negative information that jeopardizes the victim's social ties. It could occur on the target's social media page, blog, or other online platforms. Furthermore, adolescents frequently share their passwords to establish their "true friendship," which indirectly leads to impersonation (Koch, 2017).

Tricky or outing: The cyber-bully becomes the victim's buddy, causing him or her to divulge personal and confidential information. Following that, the cyber-bully disseminates or uses the information to intimidate the victim (Ashktorab and Vitak, 2016).

Exclusion: When a cyberbully decides to ban another user from his or her group of friends or a specific chat or interactive game, this is referred to as "banning." Exclusion from one's circle of friends is considered a severe type of punishment. It can result in lower popularity among peers and a fall in perceived "power" (Willard, 2007; Menesini et al., 2012; Ashktorab and Vitak, 2016).

Happy slapping: is related to conventional bullying and comprises of a video in which the victim is filmed being humiliated by various sorts of abuse and put the recordings online for other internet users to see (Koch, 2017)

Prevalence of Cyberbullying

Across studies, the prevalence of cyberbullying varies substantially. The incidence of cyberbullying is frequently determined by surveying participants' cyberbullying experiences (Capurso et al., 2017). According to a survey by Statista Research Department (2019), in the Philippines, the number of cyberbullying events was highest in region 4-A (CALABARZON) in 2019, with roughly 92.4 thousand victims. In the CARAGA region and the National Capital Region, cyberbullying and cyber libel were also more common. By 2015, a study revealed that 80% of Filipino teenagers aged 13 to 16 still experience cyberbullying (Takumi, 2016).

Cyberbullying Education for Parents

Academics have begun to investigate parental awareness and involvement in cyberbullying-related concerns as cyberbullying has gained international significance. Parents are responsible for teaching their children and teenagers proper internet behavior, which includes providing education and taking action in cases of cyberbullying (Fousiani et al., 2016). When their children reveal that they have been bullied, parents are frequently made aware of cyberbullying. According to previous research, many parents underestimate the likelihood that their kid or adolescent has experienced cyberbullying (Goldstein, 2016; Ozdemir, 2014; Cassidy et al., 2012).

According to the findings of Ozdemir (2014), parental involvement and communication may help mitigate the detrimental effects of cyberbullying on their children. Ozdemir (2014) investigated whether there was a link between parental communication, cyber victimization, and adolescent self-esteem. Adolescents who told their parents about their cyberbullying ensured they knew the cyberbullying and could intervene. According to the findings, teenagers with higher levels of self-esteem communicated with their parents more while they were victims of cyberbullying. The outcomes were beneficial when parents were made aware of their children's cyberbullying victimization.

Goldstein (2016) surveyed 110 11th and 12th-grade students about their online behaviors, voluntary disclosure of their online activities to parents, and efforts to keep parts of their social lives hidden from their parents. Participants were questioned about their cyber-aggressive behavior and whether or not they told their parents about it. The adolescent's

voluntary disclosure of cyber-aggressive activities directly impacts the parent's comprehension of cyberbullying because the disclosure results in specific knowledge of the cyberbullying incident. According to the findings of this quantitative study, higher levels of secrecy were connected to higher levels of cyber aggression and unsupervised socialization. In contrast, adolescents who told their parents more about their online and offline behaviors were less likely to engage in cyber aggression (Goldstein, 2016). Parents who are more aware of their children's online activities can better educate and influence their children's participation in cyberbullying.

Emotional Response and Coping Mechanism of Parents

To some extent, parental support can mitigate the negative impacts of cyberbullying (Swearer & Hymel, 2015). Cyberbullying experiences in adolescents are a significant cause of stress for parents. They have a severe impact on their well-being. It emphasizes the critical importance of learning more about parents' psychological processes when dealing with their child's peer-victimization incidents (Deschamps & McNutt, 2016).

Although parents play a critical role in their children's ability to cope with cyberbullying, few studies have focused on their emotional well-being or ability to cope (Tong & Talwar, 2020). Instead, most publications on cyberbullying that included a parent's perspective focused on the parents' definitions of cyberbullying or parental awareness of their child's involvement in cyberbullying. A few qualitative studies have investigated parents' emotional responses when their children are cyberbullied. They have found that parents experience anxiety, concern, wrath, guilt, frustration, disappointment, and a sense of powerlessness (Perry, 2019).

Parents advise cyberbullied children to seek aid from an adult first, ignore the child who bullied them or retaliate or promote prosocial activities. One study discovered that parents' early experiences of being cyberbullied were linked to their current attitudes and concerns about their children's school cyberbullying (Camacho et al., 2018).

Theoretical Framework

The Coping Circumplex suggests that coping refers to cognitive, emotional, and behavioral reactions to stress that are voluntary and automatic. Individuals are faced with two challenges in stressful situations: solving the issue and regulating their emotions. The two tasks relate to problem coping (describes whether a person solves or avoids a problem) and emotion coping (describes how a person manages one's emotions during a stressful situation). These aspects are comparable to problem-focused and emotion-focused coping (Stanislawski, 2019).

In the study, adolescents' ways of coping with obstacles are likely to be impacted by how their parents have dealt with challenges. The parents were able to discuss their experiences and the problem-focused coping related to it because they were able to respond to the cyberbullying issue of their adolescent with the help of other people and their support. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping can be related to how the parents managed their emotions when the cyberbullying incident happened to their adolescent.

This theoretical approach is essential because evaluating how the parents' responded to cyberbullying can help mitigate or exacerbate the problem (Saroyan, 2019). The theory can explain how the adolescent's tactics for dealing with cyberbullying are likely to be impacted by how his or her parent was able to deal or cope with the issue. Suppose the parents are unable to cope adaptively with cyberbullying. In that case, it may result in maladaptive behaviors among adolescents struggling to cope (Johnson & Ray, 2016).

Conceptual Framework

The diagram below shows how the data extracted from this study was used to develop an insight that shows the parents' experiences of cyberbullied grade 10 students during the covid-19 pandemic from different views. It starts when the cyberbullying happens to the adolescent and the adolescent's connection with the parent to cope with the situation. Through the study, the parents could voice out their emotional responses, the courses of action they took, and their suggestions in responding to cyberbullying. This all leads to an Intervention program that can help the parents to prevent and take action against cyberbullying

Figure 1. The Exploration of the experiences of the parents of cyberbullied grade 10 students during the covid-19 pandemic

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of social media is said to have increased substantially. The New York Times reported that the use of well-known social media sites like Facebook and YouTube climbed by 27% and 15%, respectively, in its analysis of social media use from web-based data sources (Engle, 2021). Physical distance measures brought by the pandemic limit face-to-face engagement, and the rising rates of social media use may be especially relevant to young people. Deprivation of peer relationships, in particular, is difficult throughout adolescence, a period of growth when peer influence and approval are crucial (Orben, Tomova& Blakemore, 2020). Stress-related with the pandemic has sparked concerns among prevention groups that it may contribute to a higher incidence of unpleasant social media encounters, such as cyberbullying. Reduced access to therapy and guidance from educators complicates the risk of damaging social media relationships. It is critical to address teenage social media use and how parents oversee their use in the current situation. (Hinduja, 2021).

When it comes to intervening and preventing cyberbullying, parents play a critical role. According to previous studies, a parent's response to a child's victimization is linked to the child's ability to cope with cyberbullying (Lester et al., 2017). Nonetheless, because children are generally unwilling to tell their parents about their bullying experiences, parents are often unaware of their child's victimization (Bjereld et al., 2017). Adolescents may hide the fact that they are bullied out of embarrassment. They feel like the problem is not severe enough and fear that alerting their parents will exacerbate the problem by monitoring or limiting their internet or smartphone use. They will then attempt to fix the problem on their own (Larrañaga, Yubero& Navarro, 2018)

According to research conducted by Rzepa&Przybylska-Duda (2016), the quality of a child's relationship with his or her parents is linked to cyberbullying. It has been found that parents who are present and willing to speak with their children are better equipped to prevent bullying and protect their children from its negative consequences. Consequently, parental warmth is linked to a lower risk of cyberbullying victimization (Elsaesser et al., 2017). Parental involvement, such as positive communication to understand the teenagers' issues and concerns or abilities to make them feel better, can protect them against cyberbullying (Elgar et al., 2014). Although positive communication does not eliminate bullying, it does help to build trust and make teenagers aware that they may rely on family members for support and adaptive methods to cope with bullying.

Unfortunately, when parents become aware of their child's cyberbullying victimization, many parents are unsure how to help them cope. The parents' responses may vary to seeking help from the school administrator or guidance counselor or by making an action themselves like contacting the bully or the parents of the bully directly (Hale et al., 2017). While there are several studies on cyberbullying, many of them ignore the viewpoints and actions of parents on the subject. This discrepancy leaves a gap in the literature and allows for future research. (Ah, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Little is known about people's cyberbullying behaviors during the pandemic and how they are associated with people's coping strategies and mental health (Biernesser, Montano, Miller &Radovic, 2020). Without meaningful action, this

could lead to increased rates of poor health, educational, and social outcomes in childhood that endure for decades (Wolke, Lee & Guy, 2017).

When their children or teenagers are cyberbullied, parents are influenced. Parents interviewed about their experiences with bullying reported more significant conflict at home, heightened stress levels, emotions of fury, disrupted sleep patterns, and a lack of control over the issue. (Harcourt et al., 2015). According to a study conducted by Harcourt, Jasperse, and Green (2014), parents are significantly impacted when their children are bullied. Because they believed they could not protect their child from cyberbullying and ameliorate the situation, the parents reported emotions of guilt, powerlessness, and a sense of failure. Parents worry that the Internet has made it impossible to effectively control their children's behavior. Parents require more support and information on cyberbullying and how to intervene and respond successfully (Buelga et al., 2017).

Even though many adolescents are victims of cyberbullying while using the Internet at home, little study has been done on the lived experiences of parents with cyber bullied children (Gündüz, Akgün&Özgür, 2021). Numerous researches have been conducted on cyberbullying among adolescents. However, minimal studies focused on the lived experiences of parents of cyberbullied adolescents during the COVID-19 pandemic and how parents provide emotional support for their children with help from people outside the family and their self-coping mechanisms about the issue.

To explore the lived experiences of the parents of cyberbullied grade 10 students of Peniel Integrated Academy of Rizal during the covid-19 pandemic, the findings of this study intended to answer the following research questions:

1. What were the emotional responses of the parents when they found out about cyberbullying?
2. What courses of action did they take upon learning of the cyberbullying incident?
3. What were the parents' suggestions that would have helped resolve the situation?
4. What intervention program can be proposed based on the research findings?

Scope and Delimitations

The researcher made various assumptions when conducting this investigation. The researcher assumed that parents would be interested in learning more about and being fully aware of their children's general well-being and that their child's cyberbullying experience would substantially impact them. The Parents have firsthand knowledge of their children being victims of cyberbullying. The participants shared their stories freely and without fear being influenced or coerced. The participants were open and honest about their experiences dealing with their children's victimization.

This research focused on parents who met the criteria of this study. They were parents of cyberbullied Grade 10 students. Parents of other cyberbullied students in a different grade level were excluded from this study. The informants of this research were the parents of Peniel Integrated Christian Academy students only.

According to research, the risk of cyberbullying peaks during middle and high school (Ioannou et al., 2017). The life experiences of adolescents were not be explored in this research. Participation in this study was limited to parents or primary caregivers of an adolescent aged 15-16 years (Grade 10 pupils) who was cyberbullied within the previous year during the Pandemic. This study did not focus on the experiences of parents whose children were the cyberbullying perpetrators. Instead of a formal face-to-face interview, each interview was conducted via Zoom Video call.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were operationally defined:

Adolescent. For this study, the term adolescents are used interchangeably with the words youth and teens who are Grade 10 students of Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal between 14 to 16 years of age.

Bullying. Bullying is the recurrent misuse of power in relationships through verbal, physical, and social behavior with the intent of causing physical, social, and psychological harm. It can entail one person or a group abusing their authority or perceived power over one or more others who are unable to stop it.

Cyberbullying. Bullying that occurs using digital technologies such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets. Cyberbullying can occur via SMS and applications and online in social media, forums, and games where people can watch, participate in, and exchange content.

Cyberbullied students. For this study, students are those Grade 10 students of Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. They have reported to the Guidance office for the school year 2020-2021 due to its profound extent and fall under any Type of Cyberbullying, as discussed in Chapter 2.

Online. Using a computer or other electronic device to connect to the Internet. Online communication includes communication that uses the Internet, such as video chat, instant messaging, or interacting on a social media.

Parent. The cyberbullied Grade 10 student's biological mother, father, stepparent, or primary caregiver.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study explored the lived experiences of the parents of cyberbullied grade 10 students during the covid-19 pandemic. A qualitative approach was adapted as the research design. Qualitative research is used to better understand a phenomenon by relying on the experiences or viewpoints of those who have gone through it. (Van Manen, 2017). According to Iared, de Oliveira, and Payne (2016), qualitative research assumes that reality is unique to individuals' perceptions and interpretations. The researcher's goal is to portray realities as the participant experiences them. The researcher used the phenomenological technique to investigate the participants' experiences in-depth. The purpose of phenomenology research is to characterize human experiences and how they were felt. A phenomenological study can assist a researcher in describing the experiences of people who are a part of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2013).

Locale of the Study

Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal is a private school located in Cainta, Rizal. The school accommodates Kindergarten to Grade 10 students. PICAR administrative staff, students, and their parents make up the Peniel community, and they all strive for excellence. They reach out to each other to resolve various concerns, allow their children to socialize with one another, and provide multiple opportunities for their children's academic, spiritual, social, moral, and physical growth through organizing meetings and varied events. PENIEL continues to improve as a learning institution in the coming years. In considering the ever-growing number of interested students from pre-school to high school, plans are in the works to relocate to a larger facility, demonstrating PICAR's unwavering commitment to provide the highest quality basic education to all. For 2020-2021, the Grade 10 students enrolled at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy are over a hundred. The study was conducted in the first quarter of 2021-2022.

Participants of the Study

The study involved eight (8) participants, four (4) mothers, three (3) fathers, and one (1) guardian-aunt of cyberbullied adolescents ranging in age from 37 to 53 years. They were interviewed through a Zoom Video Call individually with the use of a validated question guide. The participants were selected based on the following criteria:

1. They are parents or primary caregivers of students enrolled at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy.
2. They are parents or primary caregivers of a Grade 10 student who had been a victim of cyberbullying within the school year 2020-2021 during the Pandemic.
4. Participants must be willing to participate in an online video conference to share their experience.

In order to obtain the essential data that is needed regarding the lived experience of the parents of cyberbullied students, these requirements were closely followed.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling was used. According to Samara et al. (2017), in utilizing purposive sampling, participants are chosen based on "who can provide or yield data that will address the research problem." To participate in this study, participants met specific inclusion criteria. The word inclusion criteria refer to the features or traits that qualify someone to participate. (Hennink, Kaiser, & Marconi, 2017). Each participant was the parent or primary caregiver of a Grade 10 student enrolled at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal who had been a victim of cyberbullying within the school year 2020-2021 during the Pandemic. Snowball sampling was also used after finding a participant. It is a technique in which research participants recruit other people to participate in a test or study. It is employed when finding potential participants is difficult.

Exclusion criteria are conditions or situations that prevent a person from participating in a study (Boddy, 2016). Exclusion criteria also explain why a volunteer who was previously eligible for a study was later excluded. Failure to complete the interview, withdrawal of agreement to participate, or determination that completion of the interview would

cause excessive harm were all reasons for exclusion from the study. There were no volunteers who were unable to participate in this study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study was the researcher-made interview guide questionnaire. The use of a questionnaire gave the researcher a sense of order and organization. It was helpful in leading the respondents to give statements that are relevant to the study. Before the data-gathering procedure, the research instrument was validated by Three (3) Doctor of Education Teachers. The researcher began the data-gathering process only after all of the validator's instrument-specific improvements had been completed and their certification had been obtained to ensure the instrument's viability. The most important aspect of conducting interviews is creating an interview guide. To avoid ambiguity, it contains of the questions, subjects, and issues that the researcher wishes to cover during the data-gathering process.

Data Gathering Procedure/Data Collection

The researcher conducted a pre-screening by contacting potential participants via email to determine their interest in participating in the study. Additionally, a pre-screening questionnaire was used to determine whether the candidate is the parent or primary caregiver of a Grade 10 student enrolled at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal who was a victim of cyberbullying during the pandemic's school year 2020-2021. Following the email distribution, the researcher identified individuals in the population who would be possible participants via referrals.

At first, only one or two participants were discovered. The researcher then requested them to seek additional subjects willing to participate in the study. Purposive and Snowball Sampling were carried out repeatedly until the required sample size was determined.

Qualified participants received an email with an informed consent form inviting them to participate in a Zoom Video Call following the prescreening. The permission form included a detailed explanation of the study. Additionally, the consent form included a description of the interview and the data gathering process. The consent form detailed the safeguards to be taken to maintain confidentiality, as well as an explanation of the interview's anonymity. Additionally, it offered information on how the interviewee's information would be used.

The researcher conducted an open-ended semi-structured interview using a question guide approved by subject-matter experts. The respondents were questioned through Zoom video call with their agreement. The researcher created the question guide and validated it by subject matter experts. The researcher gained a sense of order and structure by using a question guide. It aided respondents in providing pertinent information for the study. The interviews lasted between 30 minutes and an hour. Interviews were scheduled according to the interviewees' availability.

Exit protocols were followed following each interview. The exit procedures included expressing gratitude for participants' participation, describing how to acquire the study's results, and providing participants with an opportunity to ask any more questions.

When the interview time limit expires without all questions being addressed or additional explanation is required, the participants were asked if they wished to continue. The interview was terminated when a participant declined to continue during the procedure.

Data Analysis

The researcher used the Colaizzi technique of descriptive data analysis to gain a complete understanding of the lived experiences of the parents of cyberbullied grade 10 students at Peniel Integrated Academy of Rizal during the Covid-19 outbreak. The Colaizzi technique is a multi-step procedure that uses an inductive analytic approach to build themes from participant responses. Boddy (2016) asserted that sample sizes of six to twelve people in phenomenological studies are frequently efficient in attaining data saturation. Each interview was analyzed by listening to it several times and reviewing the transcripts to uncover emerging themes and concepts. The analysis is the process of stitching data together, making the invisible visible, selecting what is relevant and insignificant, and connecting seemingly unconnected parts of experiences (O'Shea & Meyer, 2016). It consisted of identifying each participant's noteworthy utterances or verbalizations. These statements serve as the foundation for the analysis step, during which data categories were being formed, and themes emerged. The themes identified in this study were submitted to a participant checking technique. Each of the interviewed participants was approached individually to evaluate the coherence of the transcription and interpretation. This ensured the dependability and the veracity of the data given (Anderson, 2017).

Colaizzi's method of descriptive data analysis

Prior to the data analysis methods, the data acquired during the interviews were transcribed. The data was examined using Colaizzi's descriptive data analysis method, which is explained below (Morrow, 2015).

Step	Description
1. Familiarization	By reading over the participant testimonies numerous times, the researcher became familiar with the data.
2. Identifying significant statements	The researcher recognized all statements in the stories directly related to the phenomena.
3. Formulating meanings	The researcher thoroughly examined the crucial remarks that resulted in finding relevant meanings for the phenomena. To remain true to the observed reality, the researcher must automatically "bracket" his or her presuppositions.
4. Clustering themes	The researcher clustered the identified meanings into common themes across all accounts.
5. Developing an exhaustive description	The researcher composed a comprehensive account of the phenomena that incorporates all the themes generated in step 4.
6. Producing the fundamental structure	The researcher condensed the lengthy explanation into a brief, dense statement that retains only the components believed to be critical to the phenomenon's structure.
7. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure	The researcher asked all the participants if the fundamental structural statement accurately describes their experience. Considering the feedback, he or she may go back and change earlier steps in the analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher took several efforts to ensure the participants' privacy and confidentiality during the research method. To ensure secrecy and privacy, the researcher reduced the amount of individually identifying information that participants were needed to provide. The interviews occurred and were captured using Zoom Video Call. The recorded interviews were preserved in a Google Drive accessible to the researcher. Each participant was provided with the researcher's Zoom Meeting ID and Password and instructed to participate at the agreed-upon time. Because participants were not solicited for their contact information, using the Zoom Meeting ID protects their privacy and confidentiality even more. Individual interview recordings were numbered according to the interview's schedule. This numbering system will help to protect the participants' privacy even further. Codenames were used to refer to specific statements acquired throughout the interview. Without the participants' approval, no personal information was released.

RESULTS and ANALYSIS

The study's conclusions were derived from the participants' responses to the interview questions. The interview questions were chosen to elicit responses that addressed the study's central research topic. Each participant was interviewed using the same set of questions. The participants were asked to explain their experience with their adolescents being victims of cyberbullying. Each participant's response to the event provided insight into how they first learned about cyberbullying. The participants were asked how they felt when they first learned about cyberbullying, how prepared they believed they were to deal with the situation, and how effective they believed they were at responding to the victimization.

Informants

Eight (8) participants, four (4) mothers, three (3) fathers, and one (1) guardian-aunt of cyberbullied adolescents ranging in age from 37 to 53 years were included in the study. Each participant is the parent, or primary caregiver of a Grade 10

student enrolled at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal who was a victim of cyberbullying during the pandemic in the school year 2020-2021.

Informant 1 - P1

Informant 1 is the mother of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. She is 49 years old and is an e-commerce merchant online. She enrolled her son in the Home Education Program for the school year 2021-2022 due to the pandemic. According to Informant 1, her son was the victim of Exclusion, which occurs when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from his or her circle of friends or a certain chat or interactive game. Informant 1 became aware of cyberbullying when her kid brought it to her attention.

Informant 2 - P2

Informant 2 is the mother of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. She is 45 years old and is currently employed as an architect. Due to their relocation from Tagaytay to Cainta, she enrolled her kid in the Home Education Program for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 2, her son was subjected to Denigration, defined as sending false or negative communications to victims in order to harm their reputation or friendships, and Exclusion, defined as when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from his or her group of friends, or from a specific chat or interactive game. Informant 2 discovered the cyberbullying after noticing a change in her son's behavior. She approached him, and he informed her of the situation.

Informant 3 - P3

Informant 3 is the father of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. He is 53 years old and works as a Foreman in the Construction Industry. Due to the epidemic, he enrolled his son in the Home Education Program with Online Lectures for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 3, his son was subjected to Harassment, which is defined as repeated and offensive communication that results in significant psychological and emotional distress; Denigration, which is defined as sending false or negative communications to victims in order to harm their reputation or friendships; and Exclusion, which is defined as when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from his or her group of friends, or a specific chat or interactive game. Informant 3 became aware of the cyberbullying when his kid informed him and gave him screenshots and conversation logs of the incidents.

Informant 4 - P4

Informant 4 is the father of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. He is 50 years old and a physician. Due to the pandemic, he enrolled his son in the Home Education Program with Online Lectures for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 4, his son was a victim of Cyberstalking. This term refers to when someone is harassed, bullied, or persecuted online to isolate and intimidate them. The persecutor may contact the victim repeatedly, sending rude and intrusive messages. After hearing about cyberbullying on their group call and discussing it with his kid, Informant 4 became aware of it.

Informant 5 - P5

Informant 5 is the mother of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. She is 37 years old and is currently employed as a teacher. Due to the pandemic, she enrolled her kid in the Home Education Program for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 5, her son was subjected to harassment, which is defined as repeated and offensive communication that results in significant psychological and emotional distress, as well as exclusion, which occurs when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from his or her group of friends, or from a particular chat or interactive game. Informant 5 discovered the cyberbullying after a concerned classmate screenshotted the cruel comments in their private group chat, which her son is not permitted to join, and shared them with their adviser. After that, the adviser relayed it to Informant 5.

Informant 6 - P6

Informant 6 is the father of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. He is 42 years old and is self-employed. Due to the pandemic, he enrolled his son in the Home Education Program for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 6, his son was subjected to harassment, defined as persistent and offensive communication that results in significant psychological and emotional distress, and exclusion, defined as when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from his or her group of friends or a particular chat or interactive game. Informant 6 became aware of cyberbullying when his wife brought it to his attention.

Informant 7 - P7

Informant 7 is the mother of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. She is 49 years old and works in the medical field. Due to the pandemic, she enrolled her kid in the Home Education Program with Online Lectures

for the school year 2021-2022. According to Informant 7, her son was a victim of Cyberstalking, which occurs when an individual is harassed, intimidated, or persecuted online to isolate and frighten them. The persecutor may make repeated attempts to contact the victim, sending nasty and intrusive messages. Informant 7 became aware of cyberbullying when her husband notified her of the occurrences.

Informant 8 - P8

Informant 8 is the guardian (aunt) of a Grade 10 student at Peniel Integrated Christian Academy. She is 45 years old and is the owner of a restaurant. She enrolled her nephew in the Home Education Program for the school year 2021-2022 due to the pandemic. According to Informant 8, the student encountered Exclusion, which occurs when a cyberbully chooses to exclude another user from a group of friends or a particular chat or interactive game. Informant 8 became aware of cyberbullying after being summoned to a Zoom Meeting by the Adviser and Guidance Counselor.

The participants comprised a total of eight (8) volunteers, all of whom had their identities concealed for their own protection and security. P was utilized as an acronym for participants in the transcript, and it was numerically represented in the order in which they were questioned. Additionally, the researcher safeguarded the anonymity of the data acquired by storing the Zoom Video recordings in a secure Google Drive. After processing and transcribing the data, the researcher evaluated and analyzed each transcript. Following the assignment of initial codes, the researcher developed themes. Following each interview, participants were given the opportunity to provide feedback and ask additional questions about the research. They were informed following the study that the interview was captured by zoom and would be discarded following the study. Additionally, the researcher examined and followed up on any ambiguous comments made throughout the interview. This was done to elucidate their statements.

Because the researcher was interested in the participants' lived experiences, the following interview guide questions were used: (1) Tell me about your overall experience with your son or daughter being cyberbullied. (2) How did you address the situation of cyberbullying? (3) Did you reach out to anyone? (4) How did you communicate with your child? (5) How do you feel about your effectiveness/competence in responding to the situation? (6) What information would have helped resolve the situation? (7) Is there anything else that you would like to add about your experience? Additionally, a program of intervention was developed to address the needs and concerns highlighted by parents through their lived experiences.

Colaizzi's phenomenological descriptive data analysis approach was utilized to generate themes and sub-themes from participant responses and researcher notes. This section includes direct statements from participants to help explain how each issue came to be. We used open, axial, and selective coding to advance inductively from participant responses to themes.

Theme	Subtheme
Parent's Frustrations	Dismayed Disappointment Shocked Lack of Knowledge Lack of Communication
Inadequate Support	Sharing of Information Seeking Privacy Lack of defined process on how to address Several attempts before resolution
Proper programs and communication to parents	Parent's Support Empower the students Improve Monitoring Improve parenting skills

The themes were constructed using participants' responses to the initial prompt to describe their experience with adolescents being victims of cyberbullying. Additional questions about the participant's personal experience with

cyberbullying and the incident's impact on the parent/adolescent relationship resulted in themes. Participants were referred to in this chapter by the Initial assigned to them.

Problem 1: What were the emotional responses of the parents when they found out about cyberbullying?

Table 1. Lived Experiences of Parents of Cyberbullied Adolescent

STATEMENT	MEANING UNITS/CODES	SUB-THEMES	THEMES
<p>(P5) sumama ang loob ko nung nalaman ko talaga. <i>(I was dismayed and upset.)</i></p> <p>(P2) Tinignan ko pa siyato possabi ko, hindi ko to papalampasin, kasi nasaktan ka talaganila, and that hurts me too <i>(They will not get away with this because they have harmed you, so they have hurt me.)</i></p> <p>(P6) na dismayal ang konung malaman ko, hindi ko alam kung pano ang gagawin nung sinabisakin ng wife ko. <i>(I was dismayed when I found out, I did not know what to do when my wife told me)</i></p> <p>(P7) ang sakit para saakin, syempre, anak ko yun eh, bakit kailangan mangyariyun? <i>(it hurts for me, I am upset because that is my child, why does it need to happen?)</i></p>	<p>sad, upset, dismayed, feelings were hurt</p> <p>hurt, upset, dismayed, let down, disheartened</p> <p>upset, dismayed, confused, do not know what to do</p> <p>hurt, sad, upset, dismayed</p>	<p>Dismayed</p>	
<p>(P1) I really tried to understand yung nangyayari sa anak ko. I considered that my son could possibly have a different take on what is happening in class and his personal experiences; talagan na disappointako. <i>(I tried to understand my son's behavior, considering that my son may have a different take on what is happening in class and his personal experiences; It was disappointing.)</i></p> <p>(P2) I felt disappointed and parang I came to the point na I regret nasinanay ko yung mga kids ko to speak straight in English. <i>(I felt disappointed and came to the point that I regret that I trained all my kids to speak straight in English.)</i></p> <p>(P4) tsaka may halong disappointment dun sa mga batayanang ambully. <i>(There is disappointment in the bully)</i></p>	<p>trying to understand the situation, disappointed, hurt</p> <p>regret, disappointed, mad</p>	<p>Disappointment</p>	<p>Parent's Frustrations</p>

	disappointed, mad	
<p>(P3) Nungsinabisakin ng anak ko yung about sa bullying, nagpakitasiya ng mga screenshots and chat logs nungnangyari. Nagulattalagaakotapossyempre, nasaktanakosamganabasa ko kasi hindi ko maisip kung bakit or papanon asabi ng ibayunganunnakakasakitnasalita para samaliitnabagaylangnaman <i>(When my son told me about the bullying and showed me screenshots and chat logs of what happened, I was shocked and utterly heartbroken that other people can treat someone as horrible as this for something so insignificant)</i></p> <p>(P8) nagulatako, kasi hindi ko namanakalainnamangyayarisapamangkin ko yun. <i>(I was shocked; I did not expect that it would happen to my nephew)</i></p> <p>(P5) Parang it's unbelievable to see nayung mga students nagt team up para mangbully considering that they are all enrolled in a Christian school where, parang dapatnatuturoyung proper values. <i>(It was unbelievable how these students teamed up against my son, considering they are all enrolled in a Christian school where values are supposedly taught.)</i></p>	<p>shocked, hurt, confused</p> <p>shocked, could not believe what was happening, hurt</p> <p>shocked, cannot believe what was happening</p>	<p>Shocked</p>
<p>(P6) Talagang wala akong ka id-idea. Para bang hindi ko nakukuhayung idea ng cyberbullying napwedenamannamaglarolangsilasa internet. I thought it was simple. Kapag may nakakapang-inis o asarsayo, edi wag gamitin ang internet. <i>(I had no idea. I really do not see how these kids can be cyberbullied when they cannot even use the Internet. I assumed it was straightforward. For example, if someone is pestering you over the Internet, do not use it.)</i></p> <p>(P7) cyberbullying is real and talagang I never thought that it could happen until nangyarisanaak ko. I really learned how intense and ganokaimportanyung technology and what the effect it could have. <i>(Cyberbullying is real, and like many others, I did not believe it was until I experienced it. I realized how intense and crucial technology</i></p>	<p>no prior knowledge did not feel like cyberbullying would happen to their child</p>	<p>Lack of Knowledge</p>

<p>was, as well as the impact it could have.)</p> <p>(P2) In general, I thought like cyberbullying was only picking on other kids sa social media or Facebook. Hindi ko alamnamay gagawinsilanaganun and things like that. Yung nangyarina cyberbullying saanak ko ay iba dun saalam ko kung anoyungpagkakaintindi ko sa cyberbullying.</p> <p><i>(In general, I thought cyberbullying was only picking on other kids on social media or Facebook. I did not know that it would happen like that. My experience was quite different from what I know, and it is not the same as what I thought cyberbullying was.)</i></p>	<p>unaware, uninformed, does not understand, did not feel like cyberbullying will happen to their child</p> <p>unaware, uninformed, does not understand, not understanding the meaning of cyberbullying</p>		
<p>(P6)“hindinamankasisiyanagsasabi, sananatulonganagad, o naayosagad” <i>(He did not tell it to us, we could have helped him sooner or fixed it right away)</i></p> <p>(P2) My son had no idea that he was being bullied. He just assumed that everyone was being bad to him, so I told him, "No, you're being bullied."</p> <p>(P4) “kung hindi ko pa narinigsatawag, hindi pa magsasabiyan [his son]” <i>(If I didnot hear it from their conversation, I would not have found out the cyberbullying)</i></p>	<p>not opening up, not informing the parents</p> <p>no idea, not opening up, confused,</p> <p>no idea, not opening up</p>	<p>Lack of Communication</p>	

Parent’s Frustrations

Despite the fact that the parents were not the victim, all the parents experienced unpleasant emotional responses. Participants expressed feelings of Dismay, Disappointment, and Shock when asked about their initial reaction to the cyberbullying experience of their child. Cyberbullying experiences in adolescents are a significant cause of stress for parents. They severely impact their well-being (Deschamps & McNutt, 2016).

As a result of the thematic analysis conducted in response to the first research question, it was discovered that parents had negative emotional responses, which can be compared to some research done that the parents' emotional responses when their children are cyberbullied have found that parents experience anxiety, concern, wrath, guilt, frustration, disappointment, and sense of powerlessness (Perry, 2019).

The attendees expressed their dismay at the situation. When pressed about her feelings, P5 responded, "talagangsumama ang loob ko nanangyariyunsanak ko." Additionally, P5 reported that he was required to leave or be absent from work on specified days in order to arrange an online meeting "and speak with the Guidance Counselor and Principal" regarding the cyberbullying issue. P6 voiced his feelings by stating that "nadismayalangakonungmalaman ko; hindi ko alam kung pano ang gagawin ng sinabisakin ng wife ko." P7 also expressed a sense of being "hurt," which

lends credence to the notion of a negative emotional response. "Ang sakit para saakin, siyempre, anak ko yun eh, bakitkailanganmangyariyun?" she asks.

The participants expressed dissatisfaction with the situation. P1 stated that she was "extremely disappointed" and hoped that the incident did not occur to her kid. P2 also discussed her immediate reaction to the issue, noting, "My initial reaction was disappointment." P4's initial reaction was based on his feelings toward the bullies: "tsaka may halong disappointment samgabatananambully."

Some parents were likewise taken aback. According to P3, he was "shocked and heartbroken" upon realizing that his child had been a victim of cyberbullying. P8 added, "nagulat ako, kasihindi ko akalainnamangyayarisapamangkin ko yun."

Another issue that came up frequently was participants' impression and awareness of the severity of cyberbullying. Many parents underestimate their child's or adolescent's likelihood of being a victim of cyberbullying (Goldstein, 2016; Ozdemir, 2014; Cassidy et al., 2012). As they reported their experiences, participants made statements regarding their own understandings of cyberbullying. Their perceptions of teenagers who engage in cyberbullying, whether as victims or perpetrators, differ from the way cyberbullying is defined. This was a common point of contention among the participants.

When pressed on his past knowledge of cyberbullying, P6 responded, "Talagangwalaakong ka id-idea. Para bang hindi ko nakukuhayung idea ng cyberbullying napwednamannamaglarolangsilasa internet. I thought it was simple. Kapag may nakakapang - inis o asarsayo, edi wag gamitin ang internet. " Additionally, P7 implied a lack of awareness when he stated that "cyberbullying is real and talagang I never thought it could happen until I nangyari saanakko. I really learned how intense and ganokaimporantung technology and what the effect it could have."

P2 also discussed how her experience with cyberbullying differed from her preconceived notions of cyberbullying. "In general, I thought like cyberbullying was only picking on other kids sa social media or Facebook. Hindi ko alam na may gagawinsilanaganun and things like that. Yung nangyarinang cyberbullying saanak ko ay iba dun saalam ko kung anoyungpagkakaintindi ko sa cyberbullying."

Additionally, the students could not explain the issue to their parents adequately. "My son had no idea that he was being bullied. He just assumed that everyone was being bad to him, so I told him, "No, you're being bullied." P8, since the guardian was unaware of the problem until she was summoned to a Zoom Meeting conference by the school's Adviser and Guidance Counselor. Additionally, P4 noted that "kung hindi ko pa narinigsatawag, hindi pa magsasabiyan [his son]."

Each parent's description of their encounters with cyberbullying revealed annoyance and concern for their adolescent's well-being. According to Goldstein (2016), an adolescent's voluntary disclosure of cyberbullying behaviors has a direct effect on a parent's understanding of cyberbullying because the disclosure results in specific knowledge of the cyberbullying occurrence. Parents who are more aware of their children's online activities are more equipped to teach and influence their children's involvement in cyberbullying.

Problem 2: What courses of action did they take upon learning of the cyberbullying incident?

Table 2. Courses of Actions

STATEMENT	MEANING UNITS/CODES	SUB-THEMES	THEMES
(P5) Well, lumapitakosa family members and friends ko to like rant about it, about sanangyayari saanak ko. But then, I felt like they were judging us. Ultimately, I asked for advice from one parent to another, yung best way para I can deal with the situation without compromising my son. <i>(Well, I reached out to my family members and friends to initially rant about this situation. However, I felt like</i>	asked for advice from one parent to another, malicious talk, report, gossiping, judgemental	Sharing of Information	Inadequate Support

<p><i>they were judging us. Ultimately, I asked for advice from one parent to another on the best way to deal with the situation without compromising my son.)</i></p> <p>(P7) if you share the experience kasi with others, to larger audiences, it makes the situation more severe. We seeked help langtalagasamga school officials, sa Guidance and adviser, I think that's best. <i>(if you share the experience with others, it makes the situation more severe to larger audiences. We seek help from the school officials, the Guidance and adviser, and I think that is best.)</i></p> <p>(P2)kumalatnasabuong class nila. And of course, yungmgaparents ng anak ko, kakilala ko din, they were aware naanak ko yungnabully, siguronaging factor na din yunsakin kung bakitakonahirapannamagreach out saibangtao, syempre, yungmgaganyang issue, pagchichismisanyan <i>(the issue was known to the class, of course, I know the parents of those kids, they knew that my child was bullied, I think that is the reason why I am having difficulties in reaching out to others, I do not want others to gossip about it.)</i></p>	<p>Sharing of experience, gossiping, makes matters worse, seeking help the report, gossiping, judgemental, spreading of information</p>		
<p>(P7) Gusto ko naman din talagangmagreach out saiba, mag-open up, peroalammoyun, ayaw ko napagchismisan pa yunganak ko, in private nalang or samga teachers niyalang, perohindinasaiabangtao <i>(I wanted to reach out to others and open up about my situation, but you know, I do not want to start a gossip, I want it to be private, or maybe just the teachers, but not to other people)</i></p> <p>(P4)samga teachers niyatsakamga school staff, kasiwalanamangibang mag-aadressnung situation eh, mas okay nasa teacher nalang, mas private <i>(to the teachers and school staff only. They are the best people who can address it, and it is more private)</i></p>	<p>Reaching out to otherswants it to be private, just the teachers, but not to other people shares it with the teachers to be private</p>	<p>Seeking Privacy</p>	
<p>(P1) After the incident, nakipagusapakosamga close kama-anak para mag send sila ng message and support saanak ko para ma-feel niyanahindisiya alone. I was also contemplating kung anoyunggagawin ko, whether to reach out to the school or not. <i>(After the incident I reached out to our other family members to message and cheer up my son so that he could feel that he was not alone. I was also contemplating on what I should do, whether to reach out to the school staff or not.)</i></p> <p>(P7) Tinanong ko yung husband ko if sasabihinbanaminsa adviser or kami nalang mag solve on our own, parang kakausapinnaminyung parents nung bullies. Talaganginisipnamin kung anodapatyungmaganda steps para maadressyung issue, <i>(I asked my husband if we should tell the adviser about</i></p>	<p>Reaching out to relatives, contemplating, confused, not guided, lack of knowledge and information</p>	<p>Lack of defined process on how to address</p>	

<p><i>it or we should address the situation by talking to parents of the bullies, we really thought about what we should do to address the issue properly)</i></p> <p>(P2) Alam ko namannasyempreandyan ang teachers niya para lapitan ko samgaganitong situations pero I don't know din kasi kung paano, anoba ang steps para masolveyungmgaganito? syempre as a parent, tapos online class pa, hindimonamanineexpectnamangyayarisaisangbatayun, di ba? so walanaman formal training sapag handle ng mgaganito eh</p> <p><i>(I know that the teachers are there whenever situations like this happen, but still, I do not know the steps I should take, especially online classes. I did not expect this to happen, and we have no formal training or knowledge about these things.)</i></p>	<p>contemplating, confused, thinking of a better way to address contemplating, confused, not guided, lack of knowledge and information</p>		
<p>(P7) Sinabihanako ng adviser niyanaumattend ng conference with the Guidance but then I wasn't able to attend kasi busy sapatients. I was always rescheduling. Alam ko namanna I needed to talk to the school para ma-address. Also, nagreach out din akosa friend ko na Child Psychologist and eventually, she advised me din nadapat mag reach out or mas-ask ako ng help from the school.</p> <p><i>(I was asked by the adviser to attend a conference by the Guidance Counselor, but then I was always rescheduling due to my work schedule. I knew that to resolve the issue, I needed to talk to the school. I tried to reach out to my friend, who was a Child Psychologist and eventually advised me to settle everything with the help of the school.)</i></p> <p>(P1) There were many times din nanakipagusap kami sa teachers. <i>(There were many times that I reached out and talked to the teachers.)</i></p>	<p>attempted to contact a different specialist, asking the help of the school officials repeated contact to the school officials</p>	<p>Several attempts before resolution</p>	

Inadequate Support

One of the traits that distinguishes cyberbullying is its ability to spread quickly when it occurs on online platforms. While all bullying is defined by intentional, frequently repeated, harsh behavior aimed toward another person or group, Barlett et al. (2016) assert that some aspects distinguish it when it occurs online or through smartphone, such as the capacity to disseminate to a much larger audience. Due to the rapid transmission of information via the internet, it is difficult to restrict or prevent the spread of negative comments.

Participants discussed how they reached out to others outside the family and how others reacted when they sought to voice their experiences as victims of their adolescent's cyberbullying. Due to the exposure surrounding the cyberbullying incident, parents' memories of their circumstances caused them to believe that the issue was more difficult to address.

P2 addressed the incident's publicity and how it became widely spread by saying, "kumalatnasabuong class nila. And, of course, yungmgaparents ng anak ko, kakilala ko din, were aware naanak ko yungnabully; siguro, naging factor nadin yunsakin kung bakitakonahirapannamagreach out saibangtao, syempre, yungmgagany.

P5 also recounted a time when she felt judged, explaining, "Well, lumapitakosa family members and friends ko to like rant about it, about sanangyayarisaanak ko. But then, I felt like they were judging us. Ultimately, I asked for advice from one parent to another, yung best way para I can deal with the situation without compromising my son". P4 also

offered his perspective on reaching out to others, saying, "“samga teachers niyatsakamga school staff, kasiwalanamangi bang mag-aadressnung situation eh, gusto ko din sananglapitanyungnanaynungmanganangbullyperohindimag and angparaanyun, mas okay nasa teacher nalang, mas private” P7 stated her position on reaching out to others, adding that “if you share the experience kasi with others, to larger audiences, it makes the situation more severe. We seeked help langtalagasamga school officials, sa Guidance and adviser, I think that’s best.”

The participants' attempts at mediation were frequently hampered by a scarcity of available assistance. Additionally, it was noted that there was frequently no clear mechanism for promptly resolving the issue. P2 demonstrated how her ability to arbitrate effectively was harmed by a lack of voice help and a set procedure for dealing with cyberbullying. Regarding the incident, she added, “Alam ko namannasyempreandyan ang teachers niya para lapitan ko samgaganitong situations pero I don’t know din kasi kung paano, anoba ang steps para masolveyungmgaganito? syempre as a parent, tapos online class pa, hindimonamanineexpectnamangyayaraisaisangbatayun, di ba? so walanaman formal training sapag handle ng mgaganito eh”

P1 also revealed her feelings about seeking support for the cyberbullying event, stating, “I was also contemplating kung anoyunggagawin ko, whether to reach out to the school staff or not.”

Others expressed a wish for assistance in coping with instances of cyberbullying. Additionally, they requested additional aid from school administrators. P5 claimed that he was “happy namanakonananasabihanakoagadnung adviser about the situation, and alam ko na may care silasamganangyayari, siguro what I can suggest nalang is like a discussion about cyberbullying para hindinadinmaexperience ng ibangmgabata”

Many parents are unaware that their child or adolescent may have been a victim of cyberbullying (Goldstein, 2016; Ozdemir, 2014; Cassidy et al., 2012). To a certain extent, the parents' emotions about the situation can reduce the bad effects of cyberbullying (Swearer & Hymel, 2015).

Problem 3:What were the parents’ suggestions that would have helped resolve the situation?

Table 3. Parent’s Suggestions

STATEMENT	MEANING UNITS/CODES	SUB-THEMES	THEMES
<p>(P3) I feel like yungmgaganitong situation, maiiwasannaman eh, kung may proper na, pag communicate, or communication samgabata, tsaka they should be open or open up to their friends, saaming, mga parents and sa teachers nila. <i>(I feel like this kind of situation can be prevented if proper communication with the children can be implemented. They should be able to open up to their friends, parents and teachers.)</i></p> <p>(P1)Minsan, parang naiisip ko, like I feel like hindi effective yungginawa ko perominsan, naiisip ko na I could’ve handled it better with proper parenting, support, love, and care from the family and people around can really help. (Sometimes, I feel like what I did was not effective to my son, but then, I could have handled it better with proper parenting, support, love, and care from the family and people around can really help.)</p> <p>(P5) happy namanakonananasabihanakoagadnung</p>	<p>connection, contact, proper communication, opening-up</p> <p>not effective, proper parenting, support, love, care</p>	<p>Parent’s Support</p>	<p>Proper programs and communication to parents</p>

<p>adviser about the situation, and alam ko na may care silasamganangyayari, siguro what I can suggest nalang is like a discussion about cyberbullying para hindinadinmaexperience ng ibangmgabata <i>(I am glad that the adviser told me right away. I know that they care about the situation; what I can suggest is like a discussion about cyberbullying so that other kids will not experience it)</i> (P5) I believe that everyone should be educated about cyberbullying, and that parents should be aware of the signs and symptoms of cyberbullying para maging prepared tayo. I have two other children, and ngayonnanangyarisakin, mas may idea naakosamganangyayarikapagnaccyberbully ang isangbata. <i>(I believe that everyone should be educated about cyberbullying and that parents should be aware of the signs and symptoms of cyberbullying so that we can prepare. I have two other children, and now that this happened, I have an idea already on what to do)</i></p>	<p>care proper communication, opening up, discussion about cyberbullying education about cyberbullying, programs, awareness</p>		
<p>(P5) I wish mas naging aware pa si [name of child] about bullying, na if ever mangyariulit, alamniyayunggagawin, para hindinamaulit. We need to really train the kids to be kind to each other and hindimaganda ang pagiging bully. <i>(I wish [name of child] was more aware of bullying so that he will know what to do to prevent it if it ever happens again. We need to really train the kids to be kind to each other and keep in mind that being a bully is not good.)</i> (P2)sanamaturuanyunganak ko nalumabantsakamaturuan ang mga bullies nahindi okay yungginagawanila. <i>(I wish my child were educated enough about cyberbullying, and the bullies should know that what their doing is not okay)</i> (P4) may naituro din na life lesson itongnangyari eh, parang sa future, hindinamauulit, kasialamnani [name of son] ang gagawin”, sanaganun din saibangbata, hindinamangyari to. <i>(We learned a life lesson on the experience, in the future, I hope it will not happen again because my son knows what to do)</i></p>	<p>proper parenting, awareness, information, better understanding teaching, prevention, be kind to each other life lesson, awareness, teaching the students</p>	<p>Empower the students</p>	
<p>(P8)Dapat I am or should start namaging involved samgaginagawanungpamangkin ko online and bantayantalagakasisiyempre there are potential dangers sa internet <i>(I should start being more involved with the</i></p>	<p>involvement, knowledge, information, bonding checking online, knowledge</p>		

<p><i>online activities of my nephew and watch out for potential dangers of the internet.)</i></p> <p>(P4) Chcheck ko yung mga online games pati assignments ng anak ko araw-araw kasidapat I am responsible to see what he is doing online. <i>(I should check my son's online games and assignments daily and be responsible for seeing what he is doing online.)</i></p> <p>(P2) I know that I've been so busy nahindi ko masyadong nababantay anyung emotional health and yung online environment niyapero I want to make na he will always confide with me and open up, lalona after nung nangyari. <i>(I know that I have been so busy that I was not able to really watch out for my child's emotional health and online involvement, but I want to make sure that he always confides with me and opens up, especially after what happened.)</i></p> <p>(P8) Everything happens for a reason, siguronang yariyun para din maging aware na kami and mas maingat next time, aminadonamanakonahindi ko masyadong nababantay anyung pamangkin ko, perongayon, mas naging close pa kami. <i>(Everything happens for a reason, I think it happened so that now, we are aware, and we are more careful. I admit that I could not monitor my nephew before, but I think we got closer.)</i></p> <p>(P1) actually tingin ko naman mas nagging close kami. Mas magiging mas involved na akong ayon samagaginagawaniya online. <i>(I actually think that we are closer now. I am more involved in his activities online)</i></p> <p>(P3) That made us stronger and closer. It brought us closer together. Ngayon mas comfortable nasiyana mag-open up and mas active na akong nakakapagtanong samagaginagawaniya, parang no secrets <i>(That made us stronger and closer. It brought us closer together. Now, he is more comfortable to open up, and I can actively ask questions about what he does online)</i></p>	<p>busy, parental involvement, knowledge, information, confide awareness, bonding, closeness, closeness, involvement</p> <p>knowledge, information, bonding</p>	<p>Improve Monitoring</p>	
<p>(P5) Akokasi, I'm the type of parent na strict pero at the same time close saanak ko. Tingin ko naman kaya ko pang mag improve and madami pa akong matututunan para mag-improve tsakalalong maging involved sa life niya, especially online. <i>(I'm the type of parent who is very strict but at the same time, close to my child. I think that I can still improve as a parent and be more involved in</i></p>	<p>develop parenting skills, freedom with limitations</p> <p>parenting skills, improvement, bonding, freedom,</p>	<p>Improve parenting skills</p>	

<p><i>his life, especially online)</i></p> <p>(P6) Ayokonamanmaging super strict and parang kjna. Gusto ko naffeelpadin ng anak ko na he is free to do what he wants, syempre may limitations pero you know, I just don't want him to feel like, nanunuodako or binabatayan ko yungbawatgalawniya. But ever since the incident happened, syempre,masnaging strict ako especially sa online gaming niya. <i>(I do not want to sound strict and be like a killjoy. I want my child to feel free to do what he wants, of course with limitations. I just do not want him to feel like I'm watching his every move. But ever since the incident happened, I have been a bit more strict when it comes to online gaming.)</i></p> <p>(P4) Tingin ko kasi, parang naffeelniana I don't trust her nakapaggumagamit ng internet or nag oonline kay binibigyan ko siya ng konting freedom to use it ng hindiakonakabantay, perosyempre, I I just want her to feel safe and of course, may tiwalanamanakosakanya. Gusto ko langsiyangprotektahan, you know, para hindinamaulityungganunulit. <i>(I think she feels like I don't trust her when using the internet. That is why I'm giving them a bit of freedom to use it without me monitoring, but then I just want her to feel safe, and of course, I trust my child. I just want to protect her from the incident happening again.)</i></p> <p>(P8) Hindi kasiakomasyadongnakikialamsamga social media, ako din hindimasyadong active safacebook, kasi busy, walaakong idea naganunpalamangyayari, siguro need pa ng improvement <i>(I do not really involve myself too much on social media, and I am not active in Facebook because of my busy schedule, I had no idea that it was happening, I need to improve)</i></p> <p>(P5) I think it helped me feel more confident in my parenting...ngayon he knows na how to handle these kinds of situations <i>(I think it helped me feel more confident in my parenting now I know how to handle these kinds of situations)</i></p> <p>(P4) As a parent kasi, ang sakitnawalakangmagawa para isolveyungproblema. I am strict, syempre may pakialamako kay [name of son] peronungorasnayun para bang, ano bang</p>	<p>strict, parenting, limitations parenting skills, improvement, freedom, safety</p> <p>parenting skills, improvement</p> <p>parenting skills, confidence, improvement, handling cyberbullying</p> <p>parenting skills, improvement, strict, parenting, limitations, hurt</p>		
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<p>dapatkonggawin? Need ko nalang din siguro mas makialam <i>(As a parent, it hurts to see that you can't do anything when this happens to your child. I am strict but I care a lot about my child but when it happened I was really asking myself on the right thing to do, I should really be involved more)</i></p>			
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Proper programs and communication to parents

A study revealed that 80% of Filipino teenagers aged 13 to 16 still experience cyberbullying (Takumi, 2016). With that, it is essential that parents are aware of their responsibility in providing standards for proper online behavior to their children and teenagers, which includes offering education and action in the case of cyberbullying(Fousiani et al., 2016).

While participants described their contact with cyberbullying as unpleasant, many also reported a desire to increase awareness about cyberbullying as a result of their encounters. Participants expressed a desire for parent education in order to build a clear response strategy for cyberbullying events. Participants wanted to educate their teens about how to deal with cyberbullying situations as part of their goal of raising awareness.

While P8 noted that the cyberbullying episode was highly unpleasant, she believes it served a purpose in terms of raising awareness. "Everything happens for a reason, siguronangyariyun para din maging aware na kami and mas maingat next time, aminadonamanakonahindi ko masyadongnababantayanyungpamangkin ko, perongayon, mas naging close pa kami."

P5 stated a need for additional materials to be made available to parents. She wishes to get knowledge about how to identify and respond to cyberbullying. P5 believes that increasing parents' awareness and knowledge about cyberbullying will enable them to be more prepared.

"I believe that everyone should be educated about cyberbullying, and that parents should be aware of the signs and symptoms of cyberbullying para maging prepared tayo. I have two other children, and ngayonnanangyarisakin, mas may idea naakosamganangyayarikapagnacyberbully ang isangbata." Additionally, empowering youngsters to advocate for themselves in order to prevent cyberbullying from occurring in the future was a recurrent subject. "I wish mas naging aware pa si [name of child] about bullying, na if ever mangyariulit, alamniyayunggagawin, para hindinamaulit. We need to really train the kids to be kind to each other and hindimaganda ang pagiging bully," P5 said. We need to teach children to be kind to one another and to avoid being bullied." Additionally, P2 stated that "sanamaturuanyunganak ko nalumabantsakamaturuan ang mga bullies nahindi okay yungginagawanila". P4 stated that his experience enabled him to demonstrate to his kid how to properly deal with obstacles. P4 believes that as a result of this incident, his kid is now more prepared to deal with cyberbullying in the future. According to P4, "may naituro din na life lesson itongnangyari eh, parang sa future, hindinamaulit, kasialamnani [name of son] ang gagawin, sanaganun din saibangbata, hindinamangyari to."

Additionally, the data revealed that the participants' relationships with their teens improved as a result of their response to the cyberbullying issue. Participants reported that their consistent efforts and timely replies cemented their role as a supporter of their adolescent. The participants stated that they employed a variety of problem-solving techniques in order to act as advocates for their adolescents. Among the choices considered were contacting the school, reporting instances of cyberbullying, changing schools, and/or seeking advice from school officials. All individuals interviewed reported an increase in their involvement with their teen's activities in the aftermath of their teen's cyberbullying events. Participants reported that increased involvement in their teenagers' activities strengthened their relationship because adolescents regarded their parents as supportive of their well-being.

When participants were asked how their relationships with their impacted children had improved as a result of cyberbullying, the majority stated that they had improved. P1, for example, felt that interfering in her child's cyberbullying episode enhanced their bond. According to her, "actuallytingin ko naman mas nagging close kami. Mas magiging mas involved naakongayonsamgaginagawaniya online." P3 had similar thoughts to P1 regarding her son's relationship improvement. He asserted that he had improved his relationship with his son. After reflecting on the incident, P3 stated, "That made us stronger and closer. It brought us closer together. Ngayon mas comfortable nasiyana mag-open up and mas active naakongnakapagtanongsamgaginagawaniya, parang no secrets".

the incidents. The participants expressed a desire to communicate openly with their adolescent children. Participants said that they would continue to advocate for the safety and well-being of their adolescent children.

While sharing tales about their lived experiences, participants commented on their parenting abilities. Participants acknowledged the impact of being unaware that their adolescents had been cyberbullied. P8 stated that prior to the incident, she had no idea her nephew used social media. P8 says that if she had been aware, she would have employed additional parenting techniques. "Hindi kasiakomasyadongnakikialamsamga social media, ako din hindimasyadong active safacebook, kasi busy, walaakong idea naganunpalamangyayari." P5 stated that dealing with the cyberbullying event boosted her confidence in her parenting abilities, as she believed she handled the situation appropriately. "I think It helped me feel more confident in my parenting...ngayon he knows na how to handle these kinds of situations," P5 explained. P4 did not believe he was responsible for the cyberbullying incident, but he did exhibit feelings of inadequacy as a result of it. P4 indicated that he felt helpless and unable to resolve the issue appropriately. "As a parent kasi, ang sakitnawalakangmagawa para isolveyungproblema. I am strict, syempre may pakialamako kay [name of son] peronungorasnayun para bang, ano bang dapatkonggawin?"

According to the study's findings, the cyberbullying episode caused them to doubt their parenting abilities. Participants expressed a desire to be "excellent" parents and to give their children a secure environment. According to the Ozdemir (2014) study, parental involvement and conversation may help mitigate the detrimental effects of cyberbullying on their children.

Problem 4: What intervention program can be proposed based on the research findings?

Table No. 4 Proposed Intervention Program

I. TITLE OF PROGRAM: Cyberbullying 101: A Webinar for Parents and Caregivers					
II. GOAL OF THE PROGRAM The program's goal is to help the parents acquire helpful information on the impact of cyberbullying on the student victims and learn how to manage the real-life effects of cyberbullying to them appropriately.					
III. STAKEHOLDERS					
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Parents/Guardians - The program benefits the parents and guardians greatly. The parents can aid in the mediation and response to cyberbullying and concepts taught in the program. Students - Any school's primary focus is on its students. The program will be focused on helping the parents respond to the students' cyberbullying issues, which can provide academic, social, and emotional support to the students. Community Organizations - Creating a list of contacts for community groups is an excellent strategy to help the parents explore other organizations outside the school and to be able to reach out to other groups in the community to help them get other sources to know more about cyberbullying. 					
Objectives	Specific Activity	Facilitator	Resources needed	Time allotted	Evaluation
At the end of this activity, the learner will have an idea of the activities and flow of the program for them to be motivated to participate.	<i>Introduction of the Program</i> - Prayer - Welcoming remarks by the Facilitator - Introduction to the program and agenda	Facilitator (host) – This person is responsible for all the technical aspects and maintains the program's flow. The host will give Welcoming remarks and an overview of the program.	<i>Zoom Video Link</i> – should be sent to all participants 1 week before the program and another reminder a day before the program. <i>Prayer Video</i> – to be played during the program.	10 minutes	After the Introduction (Prayer, Welcoming Remarks, and short overview of the Program), the facilitator will ask the participants to press the "Thumbs Up" button on their Zoom App if they have understood the flow of the program and if they do not have any questions.

<p>At the end of this activity, the parents will understand the elements of cyber bullying, how to have open lines of communication with their children, and how to keep the students connected, protected, and safe online.</p>	<p>The Guest Speaker will be discussing a short presentation on “Parent’s Guide on Cyber bullying and Open Communication: Creating a Positive Digital Culture.”</p>	<p>1 GUEST SPEAKER – Guidance Counsel or from a selected school</p>	<p><i>Zoom Video</i> (Camera of the participants must be turned on) The Guest Speaker will be sharing his/her screen to show the PowerPoint Presentation</p>	<p>30 minutes</p>	<p>The guest speaker will allow the participants to share their insights on the speaker’s topic. The Speaker will call at least ten parents to share their thoughts and ask their questions.</p>
<p>At the end of this activity, the participants will be able to voice out their decisions on important matters during and after the cyber bullying experience of their child and see what</p>	<p>LIVE POLL: ACTIVITY GAME - The facilitator will give a link and code to MENTI.COM about an activity wherein the parents will see a poll about the parents’ decisions during and after the</p>	<p>1 Facilitator (host) –This person is responsible for all the technical aspects of the activity and call each parent to participate.</p>	<p><i>Zoom Video</i> (Camera of the participants must be turned on) <i>Menti.com</i> – Interactive website for the Activity</p>	<p>30 minutes</p>	<p>The facilitator will give 1 question to the parents after each round to know their opinion and thoughts about their answer to the poll.</p>
<p>other parents think about it.</p>	<p>cyber bullying incident. Example: POLL 1: Who is the first person I will talk to when I find out that my child is a victim of cyber bullying? Choice 1: my child Choice 2: my husband/wife Choice 3: my relatives Choice 3: the teacher/Guidance Counsel or</p> <p>POLL 2: I want the cyber bullying experience of my child to be ____: Choice 1: private, only the teachers and my family know. Choice 2: publicized so that others can be aware that it can happen.</p>				

BREAK TIME (The parents can have a snack or go to the comfort room before the next part of the Program)	BREAK TIME	The video being played about Cyber bullying (while parents are having a break)	BREAK TIME The video being played about Cyber bullying (while parents are having a break)	10-15 minutes	BREAK TIME
At the end of this activity, the parents will be aware of the consequences of cyber bullying and know where to get the help they need to heal.	The Guest Speaker will be discussing a presentation on “RESPONDING TO THE IMPACTS OF CYBERBULLYING AND COPING STRATEGIES FOR PARENTS.”	1 GUEST SPEAKER – Family Psychologist	<i>Zoom Video</i> (Camera of the participants must be turned on) The Guest Speaker will be sharing his/her screen to show the PowerPoint Presentation	30 minutes	The guest speaker will allow the participants to share their insights on the speaker's topic. The Speaker will call at least ten parents to share their thoughts and ask their questions.
At the end of this activity, the parents will know the proper ways to address different scenarios that may happen to a student after a cyber bullying incident.	“WHAT SHOULD YOU DO?” ACTIVITY GAME The facilitator will be flashing ten different questions/ scenarios on the screen and ask two parents for each scenario to answer the question based on what she/he thinks	1 Facilitator (host) – This person is responsible for all the technical aspects of the activity and calls each parent to participate.	<i>Zoom Video</i> (Camera of the participants must be turned on) The Facilitator will be sharing his/her screen to show the PowerPoint Presentation	30 minutes	The facilitator will give questions/scenarios to the parents and allow them to share their opinions.
	should be the best move as a parent. Example: After a month of the cyber bullying incident, you noticed that your child was always locking the door of his/her room. He/she does not go out of the room unless it is time to eat, he/she also does not want to be part of the family activities or bonding time. As a parent, what do you think is the best way to address this?				

<p>At the end of this activity, the participants will be reminded of essential questions that their children often be involved in their online activities.</p>	<p>LET IT OUT: A LIST OF QUESTIONS TO ASK YOUR CHILD The Facilitator will be showing a list of guide questions that are helpful to the parents so that they can adequately communicate with their children. Example: Talk it out...Ask you child: - Where do you spend most of your time online? - What is your favorite game right now? - Who do you play the game or communicate with the most? There will be 22 guide questions for the parents to follow whenever they ask their child about the online community. These guide questions will also be placed in a Google Sheet where the parents could have access to them.</p>	<p>1 Facilitator (host) -This person is responsible for all the technical aspects of the activity</p>	<p>Google sheet - The list of questions will be posted and updated there</p>	<p>5 minutes</p>	<p>The Facilitator will post the list of question guides for the parents to see.</p>
<p>At the end of this activity, the participants will be</p>	<p>CLOSING REMARKS</p>	<p>1 Facilitator (host) -This person is</p>	<p>Zoom Video (Camera of the participants must</p>	<p>5- 10 minutes</p>	<p>CLOSING REMARKS</p>
<p>informed of the reminders and other announcements by the facilitator.</p>		<p>responsible for giving the closing remarks and reminders to the parents.</p>	<p>be turned on.</p>		

The proposed intervention program is designed to address the parental narratives' concerns. The program is comprised of seven distinct components (introduction, 2 presentations, 3 online activities, and closing remarks). The topic covers a variety of topics, including an in-depth explanation of the elements of cyberbullying, how to maintain open communication with their child, the consequences of cyberbullying, where to seek support for healing, and coping mechanisms. Throughout each session, speakers will devote time to answering questions about parents' unique circumstances. Seven out of eight participants reported that their connections with their adolescents improved as a result of their intervention efforts. All individuals reported an increase in their involvement with their adolescent children following

WEBINAR EVALUATION FORM

Please provide us with your feedback by completing this questionnaire. This is a vital tool in our school as it helps

us to continuously improve our services to the parents and students enrolled at Penile Integrated Christian Academy of Rizal. We hope that you will be very candid in your responses as this will translate into accurate data and analyses towards better service.

Presenter Evaluation

Please rate the presenter on the following scale 1 low (poor) 5 being high (excellent) by encircling an option below.

1. The goals of the presentation were clear	1	2	3	4	5
2. The style of the presentation was organized	1	2	3	4	5
3. The presenter was well prepared	1	2	3	4	5
4. The presenter was engaging &dynamic	1	2	3	4	5
5. I found the presenter easy to interact with	1	2	3	4	5
6. My overall evaluation of the presenter - excellent	1	2	3	4	5

	Yes	No
7. Were the objectives of the webinar communicated to you?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Did the webinar meet all of its stated objectives?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Did the webinar address the concerns of your business/ area?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Will the webinar help you to improve your ability as a parent?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. Are you committed to implementing at least one of the recommendations or objectives learnt?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12. Quality of the webinar materials	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
13. Technical Support Services (Audio/ Visual setup)	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
14. Overall Satisfaction of seminar	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent

Please list 2 specific things you enjoyed MOST and learned from the webinar

1. _____
2. _____

Please list 2 specific things you enjoyed
LEAST from the webinar

1. _____
2. _____

List any suggestions you have for improving the webinar in the future.

- _____
- _____
- _____
- _____
- _____

DISCUSSION

The objective of this qualitative phenomenology study was to elicit information about participants' encounters or experiences with a particular occurrence. The participants' narrative experiences were analyzed to uncover themes pertinent to the study's research areas. The goal of this study was to examine the lived experiences of parents of cyberbullied adolescents during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the ways in which parents provide emotional support for their children through the assistance of those outside the family and their own coping mechanisms. Additionally, the data analysis showed six key themes intimately connected to the individuals' personal experiences during the pandemic. Four research questions led this investigation.

1. What were the emotional responses of the parents when they found out about cyberbullying?

Children and adolescents are increasing their use of digital platforms during the COVID-19 pandemic. Parents whose children have been subjected to cyberbullying shared their stories. The findings suggested that parents were affected negatively by their adolescent's cyberbullying experience. When they learned about the scenario, they were dismayed, upset, disappointed, surprised, and hurt, all of which are negative feelings.

Additionally, the parents were unaware of the severity of cyberbullying. A recurring theme in participant comments was a lack of awareness of cyberbullying, as individuals claimed that they did not believe cyberbullying would occur to their child until they personally experienced it. The students were unable to adequately describe the problem to their parents until they were informed of it by their parents, adviser, or school employees.

2. What courses of action did they take upon learning of the cyberbullying incident?

The findings suggested that participants believed that disclosing the incident to a larger audience would result in gossip, complicating the issue's resolution. Additionally, the participants chose to stay anonymous about their child's situation, feeling that doing so would be more beneficial to his or her recuperation. They liked that the topic remained confidential and was not made public for the entire class to gossip about. Additionally, the parents noted that a set protocol for dealing with cyberbullying situations is lacking. There was distress and debate regarding the best course of

action and who to contact in the event of cyberbullying discovery. Additionally, there were several attempts by school authorities and parents to address the issue, which ended in school transfers for certain participants.

3. What were the parents' suggestions that would have helped resolve the situation?

The participants dealt with the situation by attempting to fix it many times. The majority of respondents indicated that they would value workshops for parents and students on cyberbullying and how to deal with it. They believe that empowering students and training them on how to deal with cyberbullying can help lessen it. Parents frequently recommend increasing their involvement in their child's online activities and social media presence and strengthening their parenting skills for adopting appropriate gadget use and limitations at home with their adolescents.

CONCLUSIONS

During the pandemic, this phenomenological study examined the lived experiences of parents of cyberbullied adolescents. Participants in this study confirmed that cyberbullying affects the entire family, not just the victim. Parents serve as advocates, protectors, and sources of support for their teenagers. Despite their lack of knowledge regarding avoiding and responding to cyberbullying events, parents devised solutions to the problem. The participants' ignorance of cyberbullying demonstrates the critical need for increased cyberbullying education. While it has been observed that parents typically do not consider cyberbullying until it directly impacts them, many parents deal with adolescent cyberbullying regularly. The findings of this study may be used to argue for a greater need for cyberbullying intervention programs that educate parents on how to resolve cyberbullying incidents. The development and implementation of cyberbullying therapies and parent mediation training may have a beneficial effect on social transformation on an individual and communal level.

Simulacrum

Figure 2. The Lived Experiences of the Parents of Cyberbullied Grade 10 students during the Covid-19 Pandemic

The image above represents the themes gathered from the study. The symbol of the house represents the family of the cyberbullied student, specifically the parents who shared their experiences and how they gave their full support to their adolescent. They also shared how they got involved in addressing the issue and wanted to protect their adolescent from the dangers of cyberbullying through proper programs and communication.

The image of the clouds represents the general idea of cyberbullying. Its color is dull and gray to symbolize the negative impact that cyberbullying can have on anyone. The raindrops represent the themes that the parents felt and the complex journey that they faced when their adolescents experienced cyberbullying, like frustrations, reaching out to others, and the feeling of inadequate support from people around them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Future research should include additional studies on parental involvement in avoiding adolescent cyberbullying. While participants in this study eventually expressed satisfaction with their mediation efforts, they lacked expertise in responding to cyberbullying. A recommendation for future research is to conduct a study on cyberbullying with students of various grade levels or to analyze parents' experiences with cyberbullying prevention programs. The purpose of this study could be to interview parents of students to see how many have enrolled in existing cyberbullying prevention and intervention programs.

Another recommendation is to conduct additional research to determine which prevention strategies are most successful. This case study will assist the researcher in developing a thorough grasp of the cyberbullying issue from various perspectives.

A final recommendation for future research is to conduct a study that examines the emotions that parents may experience as a result of their child's cyberbullying experience and the counseling options available to parents to help their child avoid suicidal behavior or other severe consequences.

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